

POLY(3-HYDROXYBUTYRATE-CO-3-HYDROXYVALERATE) / CLAY NANOCOMPOSITES FOR PACKAGING APPLICATIONS

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Keywords: *biopolymer, nanoclay, thermal and dynamic mechanical properties, morphology*

1 Introduction

Due to the price increase of mineral oil and its limited availability, biobased polymers are gaining increasing interest. [1] When they are furthermore biodegradable, these materials can help preventing our planet from problems associated with inadequate disposal of waste. Moreover, there is a growing consciousness of society for our environment and the need of its protection. However, many biopolymers still suffer from important disadvantages like insufficient thermal and mechanical properties, poor permeability behavior towards gases and water vapor as well as high prices, which limit their applications to the market. Solutions have been proposed by the addition of fibers and particles to the polymer matrix. [2, 3] In recent years, nanoscale particles have shown to have potential to simultaneously increase various material properties. [4] Layered fillers like nanoclay additionally have the potential to improve barrier properties because of the creation of a tortuous path, which makes them interesting for packaging applications. [5] Moreover, clay is natural abundant and cheap.

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are a family of biopolyesters, which can be synthesized by various microorganisms, and additionally they are biodegradable. Poly(hydroxybutyrate) (PHB) is the simplest polymer of this family. It possesses a high crystallinity, which conveys him a high strength and stiffness, but also a high brittleness. By copolymerization of PHB e.g. with hydroxyvalerate (HV) furnishing poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV) some of the drawbacks can be overcome. [6, 7]

To further reinforce PHBV Ten et al. investigated the influence of cellulose nanowhiskers on the crystallization behavior of PHBV [8] and Vidhate et al. inserted carbon nanotubes for improving the properties [9]. Sanchez-Garcia and Lagaron studied the UV light, vapor and gas barrier properties of PHBV nanocomposites with modified mica based clay [10]. In a review Bordes et al. [11] summarized important investigations on the reinforcement of biopolyesters by clay. There still exist few studies for PHAs compared to other biopolyesters and most of the research is about reinforcement by organomodified montmorillonite (MMT). The effect of organomodified MMT and halloysite on the mechanical and thermal properties of PHBV was investigated by Carli et al. [12] and the degradation of PHBV / clay nanocomposites during processing was analyzed by Cabedo et al. [13]. In the published studies most of the investigated poly(hydroxybutyrate-co-hydroxyvalerate) nanocomposites were processed by solvent intercalation, which is difficult to scale up and can involve the use of toxic solvents.

In the present study PHBV / clay nanocomposites were prepared by melt mixing. The influence of clay type and surface modification on the dispersion state, the thermal and dynamic mechanical properties of the materials was investigated using natural and organomodified montmorillonite (MMT) and bentonite as reinforcing fillers. The aim of this study is the understanding of the structure-property-relationship of the investigated materials in order to be able to systematically enhance the properties of biopolymers like PHBV, thereby enabling their application in the packaging sector for replacement of mineral oil based polymers.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) was purchased from Goodfellow Cambridge. Natural and organomodified montmorillonite (MMT) with trade names Cloisite Na⁺ and Cloisite10A as well as natural and modified bentonite with trade names Nanofil116 and Nanofil2 from Southern Clay products were used.

2.2 Melt Processing

Bionanocomposites with 1 wt% filler content of the four different clay types were processed by melt mixing during 6 min at a speed of 45 rpm using an internal mixer PL-type 2000-3 (Brabender). Processing temperature was 165°C. Samples for testing were prepared by hot pressing (IQAP) at 180°C at 30-40 bar in order to obtain samples of 30 x 30 x 2.7 mm³. From these samples specimens for the different analysis and tests were cut. Additionally samples with 3% natural and modified MMT were manufactured under the same conditions.

2.3 Characterization

Scanning electron microscopy SEM images were taken with a JSM 6400 (JEOL) microscope from fracture surfaces fractured by the help of liquid nitrogen. Prior to observation samples were coated by a thin layer of gold to avoid charging.

Transmission electron microscopy was performed using a JEM 1010 (JEOL) operating at an acceleration voltage of 80 kV. Prior to their analysis, samples were cut with a PowerTome XL microtome (RMC Products) at -80°C in order to obtain nanocomposite layers of around 100 nm.

Thermogravimetric analysis TGA was carried out on a TGA7 (Perkin Elmer) device under inert argon atmosphere, heating the specimens from 50°C to 700°C at 10 K/min.

Differential Scanning calorimetry was performed on a DIAMOND DSC (Perkin Elmer). In order to eliminate any residual stresses and thermal history, specimens were heated from -30°C to 200°C and kept 2 min at 200°C. Then, samples were cooled to -30°C at a cooling rate of 30 K/min, kept for 2 min at -30°C and heated again to 200°C at a heating rate

of 10 K/min. Experiments were performed under nitrogen atmosphere.

Dynamic mechanical analysis DMA was carried out on a DMA7 (Perkin Elmer) equipment applying a static force of 250 Nm, a dynamic force of 200 Nm and a frequency of 1 Hz, while heating the materials from -50°C to 120°C at 5 K/min under nitrogen atmosphere.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Dispersion State

It is believed that the benefit from nanoscale fillers comes from their high specific surface area, where interaction with the polymer matrix can occur. Therefore, a good separation of particles and homogeneous distribution is crucial for the properties profile. Low magnification SEM pictures were taken for evaluation of the dispersion quality of the clay fillers within the PHBV matrix as shown in Fig. 1. It was found that unmodified clays, MMT as well as bentonite showed a very poor dispersion with large agglomerates, while functionalized MMT and bentonite were well separated and distributed homogeneously within the matrix, leaving only few agglomerates. In general organomodified nanoclays are easier to disperse in a matrix material compared to unmodified ones, because of their increased interlayer spacing due to functionalization. [14] Dispersion state of functionalized nanofillers was investigated at higher resolutions using TEM, and images are represented in Fig. 2. There can be seen a combination of some small remaining agglomerates and well dispersed, partially exfoliated clay layers for samples with 1% nanoclay content. Nanocomposites containing 3% modified MMT show significantly more agglomerates suggesting that for higher filler contents dispersion is less efficient.

In conclusion it can be said that for functionalized montmorillonite as well as bentonite a fair dispersion within the biopolymer matrix was achieved, while the natural unmodified fillers show no separation. This result is in accordance with the outcome of a former study on the same nanoclay fillers in poly(butylene adipate-co-terephthalate) [15].

Fig. 1. SEM images of neat PHBV polymer (a) and nanocomposites with 1% natural MMT (b), with 1% modified MMT (c), with 1% natural bentonite (d) and with 1% modified bentonite (e).

Fig. 2. TEM images of PHBV nanocomposites with 1% modified MMT (a), with 3% modified MMT (b) and with 1% modified bentonite (c).

3.2 Thermal Stability

In order to investigate the influence of nanoclay on the thermal stability of PHBV, TGA measurements were performed, as represented in Fig. 3 and 4.

Fig. 3. TGA results of PHBV and its nanocomposites with 1% of the different clay types.

Fig. 4. TGA results of PHBV and its nanocomposites with 1 and 3% natural and modified MMT.

For the nanocomposites with 1% of the different clay types it can be seen from Fig. 3 that organomodified clays (MMT and bentonite) improve the thermal stability of PHBV. By contrast, natural clays have no influence or even decrease the thermal stability of the matrix, as observed for natural bentonite. Fig. 4 shows the thermal stability of

nanocomposites with 1 and 3% of natural and modified MMT and confirms the findings of Fig.3, that natural clays decrease thermal stability of PHBV also for MMT. Functionalized MMT increases thermal stability and the increase seems independent of the filler content. It is believed that deterioration of thermogravimetric behavior of unmodified clays is caused by their poor dispersion within the biopolymer matrix, while the good separation and homogeneous distribution of functionalized clays leads to an enhancement of thermal stability of the polymer. Chen et al. also observed an influence of the dispersion state of nanoclay on the thermal stability of the polymer composite. [16]

3.3 Differential Scanning Calorimetry

DSC measurements were performed in order to investigate the crystallization behavior of clay reinforced nanocomposites. Fig. 5 represents the cooling scan of poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) and its nanocomposites with 1% of the different nanoclays.

Fig. 5. DSC cooling scan of PHBV and its nanocomposites with 1% of the different clay types.

It can be seen that organomodified fillers (montmorillonite as well as bentonite) had an accelerating effect on the crystallization, which became apparent by a shift of the crystallization peak to higher temperatures. By contrast, natural clays either have no effect on the crystallization

velocity, as observed for natural MMT, or even retarded it, as in the case of natural bentonite. Well dispersed functionalized nanoclays seem to act as heterogeneous nucleating agent due to their large contact interface with the PHBV matrix. By contrast, natural bentonite, which additionally to show a poor dispersion revealed a poor bonding to the polymer matrix (see Fig. 1), had a retarding effect on the polymer crystallization. Correa et al. also reported on the heterogeneous nucleating effect of modified montmorillonite. [17]

Fig. 6 shows the cooling scan for PHBV and its nanocomposites with 1 and 3% functionalized MMT. The better dispersed material with 1% organomodified montmorillonite seems to have a stronger influence on the crystallization temperature than the material with 3%, which contained some agglomerates due to the higher clay content (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 6. DSC cooling scan of PHBV and its nanocomposites with 1 and 3% modified MMT.

3.4 Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

Dynamic mechanical behavior of the nanocomposites was tested by DMA measurements of neat PHBV and specimens with 1% of the four different nanoclay types as shown in Fig. 7. The storage modulus is a measure of the materials stiffness.

Fig. 7. DMA results of PHBV and its nanocomposites with 1% of the different nanoclay fillers.

It was observed that the addition of 1% of all investigated nanoclay types to PHBV enhanced the storage modulus at 20°C, which is the temperature of interest for packaging applications. However, materials with modified clays showed a higher increase in modulus, than nanocomposites with unmodified clays.

In Fig. 8 storage modulus of nanocomposites with 1 and 3% functionalized MMT is compared.

Fig. 8. DMA results of PHBV and its nanocomposites with 1 and 3% of organomodified MMT.

While there is an increase in storage modulus for materials with 1% organomodified clay, samples with 3% MMT exhibited a decrease of modulus compared to the neat biopolymer matrix. Well dispersed clay seems to lead to an increase of stiffness. By contrast, the positive effect of increasing filler content in the sample with 3% modified MMT seems to be overbalanced by the negative one of increasing agglomeration of nanofillers. Dagnon et al. observed a similar behavior for PHBV / layered double hydroxide nanocomposites. In their investigations the increase in storage modulus depended strongly on the dispersion quality and the filler content. [18]

3.5 Morphology

High resolution SEM images of fracture surfaces provided information of sample morphology. Fig. 9 shows the scanning electron microscopy image of the fracture surface of poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) with 1% functionalized montmorillonite.

Fig. 9. SEM image of fracture surface of PHBV nanocomposite with 1% modified MMT.

For the well dispersed organomodified clays an increase of surface roughness was observed (see also Fig. 1), which was accompanied by new failure mechanisms. Formation of microholes due to particle pull-out (1) and ribbons due to shear

yielding (2) led to an increased fracture surface area. The breaking of the nanoparticle agglomerate in (3) shows the good bonding between biopolymer matrix and organomodified clay. Described fracture mechanisms in polymer matrices due to nanoreinforcement were also observed by Carballeira and Hauptert. [19]

Higher fracture surface area comes along with higher energy absorption during failure, improving the mechanical properties of the nanocomposites compared to the neat polymer.

4 Conclusions

In the present study clay containing bionanocomposites on the basis of poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) and natural and organomodified montmorillonite as well as natural and organomodified bentonite were prepared by melt mixing.

Scanning electron microscope images revealed a good dispersion for organomodified fillers (MMT as well as bentonite), while there was a poor dispersion for natural clay. Natural bentonite additionally showed to have a poor bonding to the biopolymer matrix.

From transmission electron microscopy images it could be seen that nanocomposites with 1% organomodified clay showed a good dispersion with partially exfoliated clay layers. With increasing filler content there appeared some agglomerates, as was observed in the case of PHBV with 3% functionalized MMT.

Bionanocomposites containing well separated organomodified clay led to an improvement of the thermal stability of the PHBV materials. By contrast, poor dispersed natural MMT and bentonite had no influence or even decreased the thermal degradation temperature.

Differential scanning calorimetry showed that well dispersed organomodified nanofillers act as heterogeneous nucleating agent and accelerate the crystallization process. Poor dispersed clays have no effect on the crystallization velocity or decrease it.

Dynamic mechanical analysis revealed that the insertion of 1% of all four investigated clay types increased the storage modulus at 20°C (which is the temperature of interest for packaging applications).

However, the increase was stronger for the well dispersed functionalized montmorillonite and bentonite.

By investigating the fracture surface of PHBV/clay nanocomposites several new fracture mechanisms (compared to conventional composites) could be observed, which led to an increased fracture surface roughness associated with higher energy absorption during failure.

In conclusion it can be said that the well dispersed organomodified clays (montmorillonite as well as bentonite) led to an overall increase of the PHBV nanocomposites properties. By contrast, the poor dispersed natural clays in some cases even decreased the polymers behavior.

5 Outlook

Optimized materials with poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) and organomodified nanoclays will be processed by twin screw extrusion and samples for further analysis will be manufactured. It is envisaged to perform mechanical analysis (i.e. tensile test) and to test barrier properties towards water vapor and gases.

6 Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support from the European Commission within Framework Program 7 for the Marie Curie Intra European Fellowship project “Novel Nano-Reinforced Biodegradable Composites: Design and Characterization” (NanoBioComp, GA-Nr. 273515).

7 References

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